

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF TEACHING ELEMENTS OF COMBINATORICS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

Shertayeva F.

1st-year Master's degree student of Angren University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14565492>

Abstract. *One of the most important components of a person's ability to think is logical literacy, that is, a certain minimum of logical skills and knowledge necessary in any intellectual activity. Since logic is an integral part of mathematics, it can be assumed that it is possible to develop logical skills in schoolchildren if we highlight for them logical concepts and actions that are present in the school mathematics course, applying the appropriate methodological processing to them.*

Keywords: *combinatorial problems solved by enumeration, set of problems, psychological characteristics, primary school students, problems.*

An analysis of methodological and psychological-pedagogical literature has shown that the inclusion of problems with elements of probability theory and combinatorics in the initial course of mathematics has a positive effect on the development of primary school students. Teaching primary school students to solve stochastic problems is very important not only for improving the techniques of mental activity, but also for developing the ability to combine, which determines the development of combinatorial thinking. Combinatorial thinking is closely related to the formation of mental operations and represents the activation of mental activity "in the direction of searching for certain transformations" (O. S. Medvedeva). Targeted teaching to solve combinatorial problems contributes to the development of variability of thinking (the focus of the student's mental activity on finding different solutions to the problem) [2].

Let's look at this example. From the digits of the number 246, you need to write down all possible two-digit numbers so that the digits in the number are not repeated: 24, 26, 42, 62, 64, 42, 46.

In the process of solving it, such a mental operation as analysis is involved - dividing the whole into parts, identifying individual elements in the object. On the other hand, synthesis is carried out - combining elements, sides of objects into a whole: 24, 26, 42, 46, 62, 64. When solving this problem by systematic enumeration, students have to classify - correlate the features of objects. They make a generalization - identifying the essential features of objects, as well as combining objects based on these features. In addition, in the process of performing such tasks with numbers, schoolchildren repeat oral and written numeration, work on the place value of numbers, pay attention to the place value of numbers, and constantly distinguish between the concepts of "number" and "digit". It can be concluded that the systematic use of combinatorial problems in the study of certain mathematical concepts will simultaneously contribute to the implementation of the developmental and educational functions of the course "Mathematics in Primary School". (Solnyshko S.V. Using combinatorial problems in teaching first-graders mathematics // Primary school plus minus before and after). [5].

The problem of introducing elements of stochastics into the initial course of mathematics is considered by many methodologists. Work on problems of a stochastic nature is given considerable attention by such methodologists as T. E. Temeriazhev, S. A. Kozlova, A. G. Rubina, A. P. Tonkikh, whose works are aimed at developing programs in mathematics within the educational system "School 2100". In the textbooks "My Mathematics" there is a whole line dedicated to solving the problem of introducing elements of stochastics into the initial course of mathematics, which is called: "Elements of Stochastics". It is mandatory and is built like traditional content lines, but at the same time has its own specifics. Already in the 1st grade, children are introduced to reading and recording information in tables, and are given initial ideas about graphs. (Demidova T.E., Kozlova S.A., Rubin A.G., Tonkikh A.P. Elements of Stochastics in Mathematics Courses of Primary School Teacher Training Faculties // Primary School Plus Minus Before and After). [8].

Combinatorial problems can be solved by various methods, conventionally divided into "formal" and "informal". With the "formal" method of solving, it is necessary to determine the nature of the choice, select the appropriate formula or combinatorial rule (the sum or product rule), substitute the numbers and calculate the result. The result is the number of possible options, the options themselves are not formed in this case. With "informal" method of solving problems, the process of compiling various options comes to the fore. The main thing is not how many, but what options can be obtained [7].

The "informal" method includes the enumeration method. This method is accessible to younger schoolchildren, and it allows you to accumulate solutions to specific problems, which serves as a basis for introducing combinatorial principles and formulas in the future. In life, a person has to not only determine the number of possible options, but also directly compose all these options, and with the knowledge of systematic enumeration techniques, this can be done more rationally.

The solution of combinatorial problems, based on the enumeration method, can be carried out in different ways, depending on the degree of complexity of the enumeration. In this regard, methodologists distinguish the following groups of problems. Problems in which it is necessary to carry out a complete enumeration of all possible options. Problems in which it is not advisable to use the method of complete enumeration and it is necessary to exclude some options without considering them (that is, to carry out a shortened enumeration). Problems in which the enumeration operation is carried out several times and in relation to different types of objects [11].

Combinatorial problems solved by the enumeration method are selected so that the set of these problems satisfies the principle of completeness. When selecting problems, the psychological characteristics of younger schoolchildren are taken into account. Problems are given according to the principle "from simple to complex", that is, the enumeration method gradually becomes more complex.

In any activity, attention, the ability to reason logically are necessary for a person, as they help solve problems, find a way out of difficult situations. Mathematics, as creativity, has as its goal the development of general rules that should be used in particular cases. The one who creates these rules, creates. The one who applies ready-made mathematical rules can create new values in other areas of knowledge. There is an opinion that special abilities are necessary for studying mathematics. But an analysis of the practice of teaching mathematics shows that ordinary average abilities are enough for a student to meaningfully learn mathematical knowledge. Sometimes

people think that success in mathematics is based on simple memorization. A good memory is necessary, but the ability to find the most successful ways to solve various types of tasks and use visual representations is much more important.

It is especially valuable to develop the ability to think logically, reasonably and reason consistently. All these abilities are developed in the course of creative study of mathematics, through solving non-standard problems, or as they are also called in various literary sources - entertaining, heuristic, creative, search, problematic, logical[12].

Combinatorics is a section of discrete mathematics that studies all possible combinations and arrangements of objects.

Tasks: 1. Understanding that in a problem on enumerating options, it is advisable to follow the logic of enumeration, and not chaotically.

2. To introduce the tool for enumerating options, the tree of possibility.

3. To develop variable thinking.

4. To consolidate computational skills.

The process of teaching schoolchildren to solve combinatorial problems conceals great developmental opportunities: on their basis, methods of mental activity are improved, the ability to combine, which is important for a person and determines the development of combinatorial thinking, is formed. Combinatorial thinking, closely connected with the formation of mental operations and representing the activation of mental activity "in the direction of searching for certain transformations" (O.S. Medvedeva), in turn, is interconnected with theoretical thinking, which is considered the main "new formation" of primary school age (L.S. Vygotsky, V.V. Davydov[14].

Thus, when solving combinatorial problems, the students' thinking activity is activated. Students, analyzing the condition, identify certain parts, make the necessary combinations. Such a thinking operation as analysis is used - the process of dividing the whole into parts, identifying individual elements in the object. On the other hand, in the process of synthesis, or combining elements, sides of objects into a whole, students determine that at first a certain combination can be made[15].

The examples clearly show that when searching for an answer to a question, students will not be able to do without observation and comparison.

If younger students do not specifically, with a specific purpose, perceive the information contained in the problem, they will hardly be able to solve it. Comparison is the process of identifying features, properties of objects and establishing similarities and differences between them - it allows students to avoid repetitions when composing numbers. Compose all possible numbers based on similarities and differences.

The systematic use of combinatorial problems in teaching is effective for developing students' basic mathematical knowledge, skills, and abilities.

In recent years, combinatorics has developed into an independent branch of discrete mathematics, the possibilities of which in applications to computers and the natural sciences are only beginning to be realized.

From the point of view of set theory, combinatorics studies subsets of finite sets, their unions and intersections, and various ways of ordering these subsets.

In the mathematical literature, three distinctive features of combinatorial problems are noted, which are as follows:

1. All objects described in the problems consist of separate discrete elements;
2. The sets of these elements are finite.
3. Preference is given to two types of operations: selection of subsets and ordering of elements of a set.

Combinatorial problems from the point of view of set theory are problems of determining the number of possible finite sets or tuples with certain properties that can be composed of given elements; or the number of correspondences that can be established between elements of finite sets. [2, 248]

Combinatorial problems are very diverse in the nature of the resulting connections. This is due to the permissible diversity of set elements and the ability to introduce certain restrictions on the objects being formed, using various ordering methods. Methods for solving combinatorial problems are usually divided into two groups: "formal" and "informal". With the "formal" solution path, you need to determine the nature of the sample, select the appropriate formula or combinatorial principle, substitute numbers and calculate the result.

The "informal" method of solving brings to the forefront the process of compiling various combinatorial configurations. And its main task is to quickly and correctly find all possible options.

Informal methods of solving combinatorial problems include direct enumeration. This is the most elementary method, since it does not require knowledge of definitions and formulas. Therefore, it is advisable to use it in elementary grades.

The enumeration method has been used to solve problems since ancient times. In modern life, it is used both in practical activities and to solve serious problems in mathematics and computer science in connection with the advent of electronic computers that perform enumeration with a large number of elements in a short time. It is important how the enumeration process is organized, since if you act randomly, chaotically, you cannot be sure that all possible combinations have been found. To avoid this, you need to perform enumeration in a certain system[1].

For this, combinatorial tables, graphs, and "decision trees" are used.

To perform a complete enumeration, so as not to miss a single combination, you can use combinatorial tables: a matrix and a numerical table.

A matrix is a rectangular table of elements. Horizontal rows are called rows, vertical rows are called columns. Matrix elements can be any objects: numbers, letters, etc.

A numerical table is a table with numerical characteristics of sets (they often suggest the best practical way to solve some problem).

Combinatorial tables are convenient to use when composing various configurations (both arrangements, and permutations, and combinations).

In mathematics, a graph is considered to express the relationships between sets and elements of sets. "Graph" - from the Greek "grapho" - "I write"[9].

A. M. Pyshkalo, L. P. Stoilova, V. V. Rozhdestvenskaya call a graph "a special drawing consisting of points and lines going from one point to another." [3, 70]

Otherwise, we can say that a graph is a collection of points, arrows, lines, loops. As N. Ya. Vilenkin points out, "points representing elements of the set considered in the problem are called graph vertices". "An arrow on a graph whose beginning and end coincide is called a loop". [5, 136]

An analysis of the features of combinatorial problems and methods for solving them allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. When compiling combinatorial problems for primary school students, various types of connections were used that are connected by arrangements, permutations, combinations.

2. The main method for solving combinatorial problems in primary school can be informal, since it takes into account the peculiarities of thinking of younger students and does not require the introduction of additional information into the program.

3. It can be assumed that the method of enumeration, compilation of tables and construction of graphs are quite accessible to younger students as methods for solving combinatorial problems.

The development of students largely depends on the activities they perform during the learning process.

If a student receives ready-made information, perceives it, understands it, remembers it, and then reproduces it, then this activity is usually called reproductive. The main goal of such activities is to develop knowledge, skills, abilities, and attention and memory in schoolchildren.

Psychologists note that the consequence of such activities is the constraint of thinking and the child's desire to think according to ready-made stereotypes. [6, 32]

Productive activity is associated with active thinking and is expressed in such mental operations as analysis and synthesis, comparison, classification, analogy, generalization. These mental operations in psychological and pedagogical literature are usually called logical methods of thinking or methods of mental actions.

Inclusion of these operations in the process of mastering mathematical content is one of the important conditions for constructing developmental learning [17].

The role of combinatorial tasks in the formation of mental activity methods can be specified using the example of combinatorial tasks that a child performs at various stages of learning mathematics. Thus, relying only on his life experience, he easily copes with such a task:

"For a kindergarten with 6 groups, we need to paint mushrooms and sandboxes for each playground so that they are different from each other. The painters only have 3 paints: red, yellow and green. Let's help the painters cope with this work".

To complete the task, each student is given a schematic drawing that depicts six sandboxes with mushrooms.

Usually children independently correlate each color with one or another element of the drawing. For example: the sandbox is red, the mushroom stem is yellow, the mushroom itself is green. If the students have difficulty, the teacher can color the first drawing themselves. All further activities are associated with the operations of analysis, synthesis, comparison. In this case, it is better to give children independence in the form of a method of action. An example of a combinatorial task, the implementation of which requires not only the use of mental activity techniques, but also certain knowledge, can be the following task:

"How many two-digit numbers can be made from the digits 1,2,3 so that the digits in the entry do not repeat?". The student, analyzing the condition, identifies certain parts, makes the necessary combinations of three digits by two, thus obtaining two-digit numbers. At the same time, he ensures that there are no repetitions. On the other hand, in the process of synthesis, the child determines that first it is possible to make a combination starting with the digit 1 - these are 12 and 13, then with the digit 2 - these are the numbers 21 and 23, and then with the digit 3 - 31 and 32. Correlating the condition with the requirement of the problem, the student does not make the numbers 11, 22, 33, since they do not satisfy the requirement.

This example clearly shows that when searching for an answer to a question, students cannot do without observation and comparison. Observation consists of a deliberate, purposeful perception of the surrounding reality. If younger students do not specifically, with a specific purpose, perceive the information contained in the problem, then they are unlikely to be able to find a solution or solve it at all [10].

It generalizes, i.e. identifies essential features of objects, and also combines and groups objects based on these features. Now the student will be able to immediately determine (in another task) the number of combinations if these combinations are made up of three objects with two elements each without repetition. Thus, it becomes possible to talk about the development of meaningful generalization in younger students based on the solution of combinatorial problems, which is characterized by the following features:

1) it is performed with such an analysis of a specific fact (task) that reveals the internal connection of its particular manifestations;

2) it, based on this connection, then allows one to immediately generalize all other facts (tasks) of a given circle, to apply the found solution method in a changed or new situation.

The relationship between the development of thinking and the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities is substantiated in a number of psychological studies. At the same time, thinking is initially built on sensory cognition, on perception and then at the highest level and development does not break with them.

In this regard, our task is to identify the main methods and types of combinatorial problems solved in primary school, select a set of such problems and examine the role of IT in solving combinatorial problems. Combinatorial problems are presented in mathematics programs of various educational and methodological complexes for primary school and are scattered throughout the course. Also, in the program of developmental education in mathematics by L.V. Zankov it is noted that "students learn to read and supplement tables, encode information in a symbolic form, make short records of problems in the form of graphic and symbolic diagrams and tables" [13].

Students also "have the opportunity to learn how to find a way to solve a problem using logical reasoning, the results of which are presented in the form of diagrams and tables." [2. p. 134] Combinatorics is a section of mathematics that studies methods for calculating the number of all possible combinations of a certain type that are produced over elements of a finite set. [3. p. 189]. A combinatorial problem is a problem that requires enumerating all possible options or counting their number. [3. p. 189]

The purpose of creating a methodological development is to generalize the experience of methodologists and primary school teachers in the formation of cognitive universal educational actions in students in primary grades through solving combinatorial problems. This collection presents a system of combinatorial problems that are aimed at forming cognitive universal educational actions in mathematics lessons through various methods of solving combinatorial problems. The problems given in the collection are presented by the types of combinatorics that are studied by students in primary school in mathematics lessons.

REFERENCES

1. Aigner M. Combinatorial Theory \ trans. from English by V. V. Ermakova, V. N. Lyamina \ edited by G. P. Gavrilov. Moscow: Mir, 1982. - 558 p.

2. Belokurova E. E. Teaching Combinatorial Problems with Tables and Graphs. - Moscow: Primary School and Education, 1993. - 68-72 p.
3. Beloshistaya A. V. Methods of Teaching Mathematics in Primary School: Lecture Course: Textbook for University Students Studying in the Specialty "Pedagogy and Methodology of Primary Education" / A. V. Beloshistaya. - Moscow: Humanitarian Publishing Center VLADOS, 2007. - 346 p.
4. Vilenkin N. Ya. Popular Combinatorics / USSR Academy of Sciences. - Moscow: Nauka, 1975. - 208 p.
5. Dzhumaev M.I. Competence- based approach to teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements in the national curriculum of Uzbekistan Science and innovation. International Scientific Journal Volume 3 Issue 2 February 2024 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694172>
6. Djumaev, M.I. Algorithm - methodological training of future primary school teachers in teaching primary science / M.I. Djumaev, M.M. Djumaeva // Bulletin of Dulyat University. - 2024. - No. 2. - P. 75-81 MRNTI 14.35.09 <https://doi.org/10.55956/MQKC8014>
7. Djumaev M.I. Competence-based approach in teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements of the national curriculum of Uzbekistan. Shymkent "KhDU" baspasy ISBN 9965-544-22-0 2024 - 306-311
8. Djumaev M.I. Development of mathematical competence of future primary school teachers in the educational process. Proceedings of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern Problems of Teaching Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in Secondary and Higher Schools" (May 16, 2024). Under the general editorship of M. Nugmonov. - Dushanbe: Printing House of TSPU named after S. Aini, 2024. - Pp. 100-106
9. Lebedeva I.P. Development of combinatorial-probabilistic thinking of primary school students in mathematics lessons: a teaching aid / Lebedeva I.P., Vlasova I.N., Kosolapova I.V.; Federal Education Agency, State Educational Institution of Higher. prof. education "Perm State Pedagogical University". - Perm: Perm State Pedagogical University, 2006. - 84 p.
10. Istomina N.B., Vinogradova E.P. Learning to solve combinatorial problems. Notebook for students in grades 1-2 of a four-year primary school. - Smolensk: Association XXI century, 2005.
11. Istomina N.B., Vinogradova E.P., Redko Z.B. Learning to solve combinatorial problems. Math notebook for 3rd grade students. – Smolensk: Association XXI century, 2005.
12. Istomina N.B., Vinogradova E.P. Learning to solve combinatorial problems. Notebook for students of the 4th grade of a four-year primary school. - Smolensk: Association XXI century, 2004.
13. Medvedeva O.S. Development of combinatorial style of thinking in teaching mathematics. // Methods of teaching mathematics in secondary school. Sverdlovsk, 1991.
14. Medvedeva O.S. Solving combinatorial problems as a means of developing the thinking of students in grades 5-6: Abstract of Cand. Sci. (Pedagogical Sciences) Dissertation. - Moscow, 1990.
15. Melkhorn G., Melkhorn H.G. Geniuses are not born. Society and human abilities. // Book for a teacher. - Moscow, 1989.

16. Solnyshko S.V. Using combinatorial problems in teaching mathematics // Primary school, 1994, No. 1.
17. Stoilova L.P. Methods for solving combinatorial problems. // Primary school, 1994, No. 1.